

Power, Annual Energy Production and CDM

River/ Villages	P (kW)	LF	AEP (MWh)	Estimated CDM (Million CER/Year)
Kalawai	19.23	0.377	63.51	35.56
Wilti	65.86	0.377	217.50	121.80
Sailala	17.14	0.377	56.61	31.70
Klawon	26.6	0.377	87.85	49.19
Batulubang	13.04	0.377	43.06	24.12
Air Besar	724.23	0.377	2,391.78	1,339.40
Nojob	108.62	0.318	302.58	169.45
Ndibwi Ndibwir	231.97	0.318	646.19	361.87
Kohoin	290.38	0.318	808.91	452.99
Sefrok	250.89	0.318	698.90	391.38
Laurin	198.37	0.318	552.60	309.45
Doros	509.2	0.318	1,418.47	794.34
Wermi	146.06	0.318	406.88	227.85
Kolam Biru	808.43	0.318	2,252.03	1,261.14
Yende	5.97	0.377	19.72	11.04
Aisandami	18.13	0.377	59.87	33.53
Naikere	7.66	0.377	25.30	14.17
Sudoy	52.05	0.377	171.90	96.26
Wowey	279.51	0.318	778.63	436.03
Weysan	374.46	0.318	1,043.13	584.15
Aiwak	275.94	0.318	768.68	430.46
Sudik	75.21	0.377	248.38	139.09
Bengko	38.7	0.377	127.81	71.57
Sosmorof	93.43	0.377	308.55	172.79
Kopo	7.45	0.377	24.60	13.78
Sururey	12.37	0.377	40.85	22.88
Hingk	16.11	0.377	53.20	29.79
Demaisi	28.14	0.377	92.93	52.04
Indabri	33.6	0.377	110.96	62.14
Inggen	40.79	0.377	134.71	75.44
	4,769.54	10.66	13,956.09	7,815.41

